

LEARNERS' DIFFICULTIES IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE ACQUISITION

Abstract:

Nowadays, it is commonly understood that language skills are essential to the development of all knowledge. People are increasingly conscious of other cultures and languages as a result of greater migration and movement worldwide. This highlights how crucial it is to learn English as a global language. The majority of students nowadays are having trouble studying English as a foreign language. These problems will be covered in this article, along with explanations of their causes.

Key words:

Foreign language, language acquisition, speaking difficulties, writing difficulties, reading difficulties, listening difficulties.

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Introduction. Since English is one of the most commonly spoken languages in the world, it is viewed and utilized as an international language. Since then, it has become more and more widespread, and today practically everyone on the earth speaks and understands it. Many people make an effort to learn English because of a number of factors. Finding work, traveling, talking with others, conducting business, passing a test, conducting research, and writing in a foreign language are a few of them.

One's life experiences can be improved by learning English. It is a sophisticated cognitive process that combines speaking, reading, listening, and writing. A second language may be learned in one of two ways, according to linguist Stephen Krashen: by learning the language's rules, structures, and vocabulary, or by "acquiring" it, like a toddler does if they grow up hearing many languages spoken regularly (Krashen, 1982). A new language might be picked up more quickly and effortlessly by certain pupils than others. Everyone who has studied a foreign language for themselves or has had the opportunity to teach others who are doing the same in school is aware of this basic reality. It is obvious that some language learners succeed because of their unwavering willpower, perseverance, and hard effort. The topic of difficulties in language acquisition has been investigated by many scholars. According to Susmiati's (2003) investigation, some pupils struggle to pronounce words word by word since they haven't had much exposure to English. Due of their conduct,

pupils' challenges with English as a foreign language have been researched by Andrea (2006). Melinda Roza (2012) looked on the differences between learning a second language and learning a first language.

Research results. The process of acquiring a first or second language is called language acquisition. Psycholinguists and developmental psychologists are the main researchers who examine how people learn new languages, including English. Although the exact process by which children learn to speak is not fully understood, the majority of explanations include both the finding that children mimic what they hear and the implication that humans have a built-in aptitude for grammar (David, 2010).

Factors that affect on the foreign language acquisition

An internal component and an external factor both have an impact on the student's struggles with learning the English language. Internal elements are those that each language learner individually contributes to the specific learning environment.

Age has an impact on a learner's capacity to pick up the English language. Children who are already proficient readers in their native tongue appear to be in the greatest placed to pick up other languages quickly. However, they frequently fail to produce pronunciation and intonation that is similar to that of a native speaker. Motivated older students can also achieve great results.

Personality also impacts how students learn a second or foreign language. Introverted or worried students typically advance more

slowly, especially when developing speech abilities. They are less inclined to actively seek out speaking chances or to seize them when they present themselves. Less shy kids won't stress over the likelihood of making blunders. They will take chances, giving themselves a lot more practice in the process.

A level of motivation also is responsible for language acquisition. Extrinsic and intrinsic motives both exist. It has been discovered that intrinsic motivation closely correlates with academic success. Students who take pleasure in their achievements and love learning a new language will undoubtedly perform better than those who do not. The importance of extrinsic motivation cannot be overstated. ESL students, for instance, are more likely to put out more effort and thus make more progress if they need to study English in order to enroll in an American institution or converse with a new English boyfriend or girlfriend.

Difficulties students face across four primary skills' development

Speaking difficulties

According to Zhang's (2009) argument, speaking is still the most challenging ability for most English language learners to acquire, and they are still unable to effectively communicate verbally in the language. Students are anxious about making mistakes, afraid of criticism, or just bashful, claims Ur (1996). Students can lack the motivation to express themselves, and low or unequal involvement is another problem. Due to the size of the courses, only one person can speak at once.

Mother-tongue use also has a negative impact on the development of speaking abilities, as does the tendency of certain students to dominate while others talk very little or not at all. Because it is simpler and seems less vulnerable when spoken, learners who share the same mother language frequently utilize it. Some of these elements have to do with the students themselves, the curriculum, the environment, and the methods of instruction.

For instance, many students are unable to continue an engagement because they lack the language needed to communicate their meaning. Another cause for not being able to maintain the relationship is a lack of strategy and communication ability. This issue is exacerbated by ineffective teaching methods that place little value on speaking, which leads to the weak development of this talent. In addition, because there are more instructors than there are cassettes available, vocabulary words are taught separately, and most teachers do not use listening resources. It was discovered that teacher-training programs were not particularly effective at changing the teaching style of the instructors.

Writing difficulties

The ability to write well is crucial for language creation. However, it is regarded as a challenging talent, especially in situations when pupils are learning English as a foreign language (EFL), where they confront several writing obstacles. The hardest part of learning a second language is writing. It is based on the strategic and suitable use of language that has the ability to communicate and is accurate structurally (Dar & Khan, 2015). Throughout their learning process, students who write encounter a variety of writing issues. These issues may often be broken down into linguistic, psychological, cognitive, and pedagogical categories (Haider, 2012). These are linked to the motivation of students who are typically unsure about the meaning and goal of their texts in their L2 studies. Similar to this, social media, inconsistent instructor feedback, learners' lack of an analytical and critical attitude, and big and unmanageable class numbers all have a detrimental effect on how accurately the texts of the students are written in terms of structure and communication. The majority of students find it extremely difficult to gather enough reliable source material, summarize or paraphrase knowledge, and write in an appropriate academic voice. It is a result of inadequate communication between students and teachers regarding the proactive measures that should be taken to address these issues, delayed instruction

in essay writing, large classes, students' negative attitudes toward their academic English course, L1 transfer, and delayed instruction in essay writing.

Listening difficulties

One of the most crucial abilities in learning the English language is listening. Students encounter several hearing challenges when they listen to the English language. Students struggle greatly with listening comprehension because academic institutions place greater emphasis on writing, reading, and vocabulary. Many course manuals place little emphasis on listening, and most instructors do not emphasize this crucial ability in their lessons. Difficulties may arise for the following reasons. Some professors utilize low-quality recorded materials in their lessons. The audio system's quality might affect how well students can understand what they are hearing. Learners should be aware of the cultural aspects of language that greatly influence their comprehension. The students may have serious understanding issues if the listening exercise uses content from a completely different cultural background. Teachers must provide students background information about the listening exercises beforehand. Unfamiliar accents, both native and non-native, can seriously hinder learners' listening comprehension, therefore getting to know an accent is beneficial (Buck, 2001). Unfamiliar vocabulary can also be a problem for students. If students know the meaning of words, this can pique their interest and motivation and can have a positive impact on the students' listening comprehension ability. At the same time, an unfamiliar accent makes comprehension impossible for the listeners. Since many words have several meanings, pupils will become perplexed if they are not utilized correctly in the right settings.

Reading difficulties

A great number of students without sufficient vocabulary knowledge or effective learning strategies mostly face reading comprehension difficulties.

This is because students with poor vocabulary knowledge face difficulties in understanding technical words such as superordinate, synonyms, antonyms, or words with multiple connotations. Text complexity influences reading comprehension. Meaning that, learners' fluency in language enables them to have more in-depth understanding of text. Hence, oral ability is prominent when it comes to recognize how skilled a reader can be since students acquire new vocabulary through listening. Having adequate vocabulary helps students in clarifying the strange words by relating them with the context in which they are used. Another problem facing EFL learners is ability to understand complex sentences in reading comprehension. Complex sentences are sentences that consist of several clauses, and at times contain conjunctions such as although, because, furthermore, and however. Other causes of difficulties in reading comprehension among EFL learners include coordinating conjunctions, prepositional phrases, participial phrases, and nominalizations. They cause a lot of difficulties in reading comprehension because they make the writings more complex and difficult to comprehend. Useful learning methods, reading habits, text form, and effective reading comprehension strategies can help solve these problems.

Conclusion. By encouraging students' interest, drive, and enjoyment of writing, technology can help students avoid difficulties. Similar to this, several metacognitive, cognitive, and socio-affective techniques may be employed to help students understand and practice their skills. Further, Teachers may adjust their educational strategies and work together to develop objectives. Through prolonged practice and the use of physical and mental abilities that provide the learner control over the expression of language and subject-specific information, it is likely to modify their learning habits.

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